

NEUROCLIMA

Deliverable D7.5

Proceedings of NEUROCLIMA
workshops and summary
report on cohesion activities

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Full name
AI	Artificial Intelligence
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
NAM	Norm Activation Model
TTM	Transtheoretical Model
SDT	Self-Determination Theory

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the first round of dissemination and cohesion actions carried out under Task 7.3 of the NEUROCLIMA project. It captures the planning, implementation, and preliminary outcomes of internal and external workshops, alongside efforts to establish meaningful synergies with EU-funded projects working on climate resilience, behavioural change, and citizen participation.

Three main components are included:

- **Internal Partner Workshops** served to align ethical standards, refine behavioural change methodologies, and introduce inclusive facilitation tools. These sessions helped consolidate a shared understanding across the consortium and informed the co-creation of field methods to be piloted later.
- **External Online Workshop** (“Climate Resilience Blueprints”) opened NEUROCLIMA’s digital tools to a wider audience. With 95 registrants from 24 countries and 51 confirmed participants, the workshop featured live demonstrations of NEUROCLIMA’s AI-supported tools and gathered direct feedback from educators, policymakers, civil society, and researchers. The interactive format reinforced the importance of accessibility, scientific trust, and human moderation in digital engagement processes.
- **Synergistic Activities and Project Mapping** identified and connected NEUROCLIMA with relevant EU initiatives. Informative outreach was conducted, and bilateral collaboration meetings were held with two major projects: **Pro-Climate**, which focuses on behavioural tipping points and policy actions for community adaptation, and **Mission4Adapt**, which supports inclusive governance and regional engagement in climate action. Additionally, more than 15 other related projects were mapped to inform future joint actions.

Key early insights include the central role of human-centred facilitation, the limitations of digital-only strategies, and the need to clearly link participation to impact. These findings shape the next steps of NEUROCLIMA’s engagement strategy, which will include in-person sessions, targeted follow-up with workshop participants, and deepened collaboration with the wider European climate adaptation ecosystem.

D7.5 serves not only as documentation but also as a learning interface. It lays the foundation for future deliverables and supports the project’s broader aim to design inclusive, adaptive, and trust-based pathways toward behavioural and systemic transformation in the face of climate change.

1. Introduction

This report brings together the main activities and reflections of Task 7.3, which focuses on workshops and cohesion actions across the NEUROCLIMA consortium. So far, we've hosted internal workshops with all partners and delivered one online external workshop. These early steps allowed us to map our shared vision, shape the facilitation strategy, and start building a community of practice around behavioural change and climate adaptation.

The work is ongoing. This deliverable offers a first glimpse of the evolving strategy and outlines where we stand, what we've achieved, and what's coming next.

The deliverable is structured in three parts:

1.1 Objectives of the Deliverable

The main goal of Deliverable D7.5 is to document the planning and first round of activities carried out under Task 7.3. These include:

- The organisation and facilitation of stakeholder and internal workshops.
- The initiation of cohesion activities, particularly through our early online event and targeted partner engagements.
- The establishment of synergies with related EU projects and initiatives working on environmental and climate adaptation.

More broadly, D7.5 acts as a strategic entry point to:

- Share what has worked so far and what still needs refining.
- Provide an open space for reflection on how to engage different audiences meaningfully.
- Build the groundwork for Deliverables D7.6, which will document external synergies and cross-project cohesion actions in more depth.

1.2 Methodological Approach

Our approach combines facilitation, knowledge sharing and stakeholder mobilisation, always anchored in the NEUROCLIMA logic. The structure follows three interlinked steps:

Step 1: Internal Alignment: Early internal workshops were held among partners to set common ground. These included discussions on ethical standards, facilitation techniques, behavioural change strategies, and the use of AI-supported civic tools. These workshops helped to define what “cohesion” means in our context—not only coordination, but a shared sense of responsibility and contribution.

Step 2: First External Engagement: An online workshop was delivered with external participants, marking the first attempt to open up the internal workstreams. Participants included local actors, youth workers, climate practitioners and civic tech experts. The session focused on what a “climate-theme-sensitive” deliberation service looks like in practice and tested some early design assumptions.

Step 3: Integration and Learning: Insights from both internal and external activities were summarised and discussed collectively. Particular attention was given to challenges such as stakeholder fatigue, digital accessibility, and intercultural facilitation. These findings informed the design of upcoming training sessions and the refinement of facilitation protocols.

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All workshops followed an inclusive structure and were designed using adaptive learning tools. The process was flexible, iterative, and partner-led—aligning well with the double diamond and co-design principles used throughout NEUROCLIMA.

behavior

1.3 Key Insights and Preliminary Reflections

Several early insights emerged from our work so far:

- **The value of moderation:** A strong, human-centred facilitation process is critical. Even in digital settings, human moderation makes a difference in how participants engage and respond.
- **The limits of digital-only strategies:** Not all target groups have equal access or familiarity with online tools. This reinforces the need for blended approaches—combining online tools with on-the-ground community involvement.
- **Cohesion needs a purpose:** Collaboration should not be forced. It needs to be meaningful and tied to shared goals. In our case, behavioural change and civic trust are the anchors.
- **Linking knowledge to action:** Stakeholders want to see the link between participation and real change. Providing that connection—through feedback loops, visualisations, or policy relevance—is key.

These lessons will shape the design of the next workshops, including the in-person training sessions planned for the final year. We will also deepen our work with aligned EU-funded projects and networks, using shared methodologies and facilitation frameworks.

2. Introduction

This report marks a key point in the development of NEUROCLIMA’s participatory and cohesion actions. While much of the project focuses on research, behavioural analysis and tool development, D7.5 captures something different: the way people, partners and ideas start connecting in practice. It brings together the early steps we’ve taken to build trust, test methods, and create inclusive pathways into the project’s long-term goals.

The document outlines both the actions taken so far and the strategic foundations for upcoming steps. It is not a static deliverable, but part of a process that is unfolding and evolving with every workshop, conversation, and learning loop.

2.1. Context within the NEUROCLIMA Project

NEUROCLIMA was designed to respond to a clear gap: while there are many technical tools for climate monitoring and decision-making, there is often a missing link between these tools and the people they’re meant to serve. The project’s vision is to build a kind of nervous system—an interconnected set of tools, and participatory processes that allow citizens, institutions and technologies to engage in meaningful, ongoing interactions that foster sustained behavioural change.

At the heart of this vision is the idea of **behavioural tipping points**: the small, often personal changes that, when supported and scaled, can lead to broader systemic shifts. This is where human participation becomes central. For AI-enhanced systems to be trusted and useful, they must be shaped by the people who use them. That is why workshops, deliberative sessions and civic engagement activities are not secondary, but core components of NEUROCLIMA.

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Task 7.3 belongs to **Work Package 7**, which deals with dissemination, exploitation, promotion and stakeholder participation. Within this WP, Task 7.3 focuses specifically on designing and delivering activities that bring people together, both within the consortium and across external communities. It complements the technical work by grounding it in real-world interaction.

So far, this has meant facilitating internal workshops, planning public-facing events, and building links with similar projects across Europe. These efforts will continue to grow as the pilots launch and tools are tested in practical settings.

2.2. Role of D7.5 in the Dissemination and Cohesion Strategy

D7.5 plays a very specific role in NEUROCLIMA's wider strategy: it brings the early participatory work into focus, documents it, and uses it to guide future steps. While other deliverables from WP7 focus on communication materials (D7.1), exploitation strategies (D7.2), and training modules (D7.4), this one looks at the **experience of interaction**.

It covers both internal and external aspects:

- **Internally**, it supports partner coordination, capacity-building and shared understanding.
- **Externally**, it contributes to raising awareness, identifying early adopters, and testing whether our methods resonate with real-world stakeholders.

Crucially, D7.5 also supports the **cohesion mission** of NEUROCLIMA: helping people feel that they are part of a shared process. This means more than outreach. It involves careful listening, co-creation, and dialogue across different sectors and backgrounds.

In doing so, D7.5 feeds directly into:

- The refinement of the dissemination strategy (T7.1)
- The market positioning of the tools and services developed (T7.2)
- The alignment of NEUROCLIMA with EU adaptation goals and policy frameworks (T7.5)
- The integration of lessons learnt into training and guidance packages (T7.4)

It also helps shape upcoming deliverables D7.6 and D7.8, where common practices and shared engagement frameworks with other projects will be described.

2.3. Structure of the Report

This deliverable is organised in five main parts:

- **Section 1 – Executive Summary** provides a concise overview of the deliverable's purpose, methods and key findings to date.
- **Section 2 – Introduction** (this section) sets the scene by explaining where D7.5 sits within the wider project and what it aims to do.
- **Section 3 – Overview of Implemented Workshops** describes the internal and external workshops held to date, outlining their structure, themes, outcomes and formats.
- **Section 4 – Preliminary Reflections on Cohesion Activities** explores what we've learnt so far about building engagement, trust and collaboration across the different NEUROCLIMA audiences.
- **Section 5 – Next Steps and Strategic Directions** outlines how the insights from this phase will shape the next round of events and cohesion actions, including links with EU partners, policy initiatives and local stakeholders.

Annexes include sample agendas, participant lists (anonymised), feedback forms and selected workshop outputs.

3. Overview of Implemented Workshops

3.1 Internal Workshops with Project Partners

NEUROCLIMA's internal workshops served as structured co-learning spaces to exchange knowledge, refine methodologies, and align partners on the conceptual and practical dimensions of behavioural climate adaptation. Two main workshops were held during the reporting period, each with a distinct thematic and methodological focus.

The first internal webinar, held on **12 November 2024 (09:00–11:00 CET)**, brought together project partners from IASIS, CEPS, and POLIMI for a multidisciplinary exchange. IASIS presented core behavioural change frameworks, including the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), the Norm Activation Model (NAM), the Transtheoretical Model (TTM), and Self-Determination Theory (SDT). These models were not introduced in isolation but as interrelated lenses to interpret behavioural transformation in climate contexts. IASIS emphasised the added value of combining behavioural theories with systemic and technological tools, such as AI-driven feedback systems, gamified interventions, and real-time monitoring mechanisms. Ethical concerns, including digital inclusion, emotional balance in messaging, and privacy considerations, were explicitly addressed.

CEPS followed with a practical orientation on the **EU Artificial Intelligence Act**, highlighting its implications for NEUROCLIMA's chatbot and generative tools. The presentation clarified the project's current positioning within the "limited risk" tier of the AIA and encouraged all partners to consider ethical obligations, transparency requirements, and compliance mechanisms.

POLIMI concluded the session by framing **data visualisation as a constructive tool** for knowledge production and participatory reflection. Drawing on the metaphor of "sandcastles," the team illustrated how visualisation supports speculation, shared understanding, and critical engagement. Aesthetic and interpretive approaches were foregrounded, including visual metaphors and collaborative mapping. Partners explored how these tools might support the project's aims, particularly in relation to engagement and evaluation.

The second internal workshop, organised by IASIS on **26 March 2025**, focused on the creative dimension of behavioural engagement and its application within Work Package 3. Two methods were presented in detail: **cinematherapy** and **creative writing**. In this context, POLIMI also provided a presentation dedicated to the role of digital technology and Artificial Intelligence in sustainability and deliberation processes, presenting a collection of case studies.

Cinematherapy was introduced not simply as a film screening activity, but as an immersive, emotionally resonant process that fosters symbolic thinking, agency, and critical dialogue. IASIS described a stepwise pedagogical path: from ethical preparation and film selection, to guided reflection, metaphorical exploration, and integration into personal or community action. The technique emphasised inclusivity, consent, emotional safety, and the creation of a shared space where participants could articulate their lived experiences in relation to climate change. A strong rationale connected this process with emotional regulation, critical media literacy, and storytelling as a mode of civic participation.

Creative writing was presented as an equally accessible and empowering method. Through prompts such as "Write a letter to the Earth from the year 2050" or "If climate change were a person, what

would you say to them?”, the method encouraged introspection, narrative agency, and emotional articulation. Key stages of the method—trust-building, expression, optional sharing, reflection, and integration—were mapped out, highlighting the tool’s relevance across age groups and literacy levels. Emphasis was placed on the emotional and symbolic dimensions of writing, and its role in enabling personal insight and collective dialogue.

To strengthen the connection between WP3 and WP5, a literature synthesis on the role of digital technology and AI in sustainability and deliberation processes was conducted to distill the key themes, research methodologies, and implications for sustainability and climate change. This analysis was then juxtaposed with targeted case studies and established frameworks, demonstrating how such precedents informed the design of the NEUROCLIMA Integrated Solution.

Both sessions were rooted in NEUROCLIMA’s goal of fostering inclusive behavioural and systemic change through emotionally intelligent, ethically aware, and practically grounded tools. These workshops not only strengthened internal alignment but also laid the foundation for piloting creative methods in diverse field contexts under WP5 and WP6.

3.2 Online Workshop – Public Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement

3.2.1 Objectives and Target Groups

The first stakeholder workshop aimed to introduce the core ideas and digital tools of the NEUROCLIMA project. Rather than just being a presentation, it was our first real attempt to open up our work to public review, gather honest feedback and begin to build lasting connections with our target audience.

The session focused on two main areas:

1. Showcasing key outputs from Work Package 3, specifically D3.1 and D3.3, which are both foundational to our vision of behavioural and systemic change.
2. The second area was presenting early versions of the digital ecosystem being developed under Work Package 5 and testing initial reactions from diverse audiences.

The event was designed for people from a variety of backgrounds. We invited educators, researchers, local officials, civil society actors, journalists and environmental professionals. Climate policy stakeholders and organisations already involved in EU-funded environmental projects were also included on the list. Our goal was to bring together a variety of perspectives to help shape NEUROCLIMA’s tools in a meaningful and practical way.

3.2.2 Agenda and Preparation

The online event “**Climate Resilience Blueprints: A First Look at NEUROCLIMA’s Digital Solution**” took place on April 29, 2025, from 15:30 to 17:00 CET. The timing was carefully chosen: after the Easter holidays, when most participants had returned to regular schedules but before the busy period of May commitments. Holding the workshop on a Tuesday afternoon also allowed for greater participation, balancing between work responsibilities and personal obligations.

The event was hosted via the IASIS professional Zoom account, ensuring a stable technical environment and full access to advanced hosting features. The platform was selected for its familiarity among participants and its reliability for managing interactive sessions.

The final structure of the agenda was organised to provide a clear, engaging flow across different aspects of the NEUROCLIMA project:

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1. Introduction to NEUROCLIMA and Social Tipping Points
 - Presenter: Dr. Beatrice Gobbo (Politecnico di Milano, Department of Design)
 - Duration: 15 minutes
 - A focused presentation linking climate resilience efforts with behavioural dynamics.
2. Creative Arts Toolkits
 - Presenter: Dr. Stefanos Alevizos (Postdoctoral Researcher | Psychologist, IASIS)
 - Duration: 15 minutes
 - An overview of the creative approaches developed to support citizen engagement.
3. A First Look at Our Digital Solution
 - A series of short, targeted presentations introduced key elements of the NEUROCLIMA platform:
 - Introduction to NEUROCLIMA solution (intended users, main objectives, overview of applications) + NeuroClimaPortal
 - Presenter: Tassos Kanellos (ITML) | 10 minutes
 - NeuroClimaLens
 - Presenter: Tassos Kanellos (ITML) | 5 minutes
 - NeuroClimaBot
 - Presenter: Prasasthy Kumarankunnath Balasubramanian (University of UOULOU, UBICOMP/ITEE) | 5 minutes
 - NeuroClimaDialogues
 - Presenter: Giorgios Domalis (Novelcore) | 5 minutes
 - NeuroClimaLearn
 - Presenter: Antonis Batsos (Epsilon International Ltd) | 5 minutes
 - NeuroClimaPlay
 - Presenter: Kemi Oyesola (Infinitivity Design Labs) | 5 minutes
 - Final survey questions
 - Presenter: Tassos Kanellos (ITML) | 5 minutes

The session moderator was selected in advance: Christina Deligianni (Senior Advisor, Truenique), chosen for her experience in facilitating professional online discussions. Her role was planned to include not only guiding the event but also leading the open discussion session with the participants. Based on the timing of the agenda, with presentations expected to last around 70 minutes, the remaining time was allocated for audience interaction. The plan was to create an open space where participants could share feedback, raise questions, and exchange views on the NEUROCLIMA digital solutions.

The promotional campaign for the workshop started on **April 21, 2025**. The invitation text was co-developed by **IASIS**, **POLIMI**, and **EPSILON**, aiming to present the scope and structure of the event clearly while encouraging participation from relevant audiences. The announcement was titled:

Climate Resilience Blueprints: A First Look at NEUROCLIMA's Digital Solution
April 29, 2025 | 15:30 – 17:00 CET | Online

The message highlighted NEUROCLIMA's work on a digital "nervous system" that brings together artificial intelligence, citizen engagement, and educational experiences. It invited attendees to interact with early prototypes of the platform and contribute to its development through discussion and real-time feedback.

Registrations remained open until the day of the event, and participation was free of charge. The invitation was shared through a coordinated outreach campaign across multiple channels:

- **Email distribution** to the networks of all project partners.

- **Social media** dissemination (Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, X) through NEUROCLIMA's official accounts. The visuals and layout were designed by **João Carlos Nunes**, Communications Officer at **Re-Imagine Europa**, ensuring consistency with the project's visual identity.
- **Consortium-wide promotion**: All partners circulated the invitation within their institutional and professional networks, both national and European.
- **Targeted outreach** to selected educators, journalists, and policy stakeholders, including **EU Climate Pact Ambassadors through the Truenique database**.

In addition, direct invitations were sent to specific categories of stakeholders via targeted emails:

1. **Environmental Education Centers**. A large portion of the outreach focused on **Environmental Education Centers (Κέντρα Περιβαλλοντικής Εκπαίδευσης - ΚΠΕ)** across Greece. These centers operate under the Ministry of Education and play a central role in environmental awareness and sustainability training for students and the public.
2. **Academia and Research Institutions**. Emails were also addressed to **university professors, researchers, and research networks** active in climate change, sustainability, environmental sciences, and related disciplines.
3. **Policy Makers and Governance Actors**. Selected **local and regional government representatives**, including prefectural and municipal authorities involved in environmental planning and education, were invited to participate.
4. **Civil Society and Non-Governmental Organizations**. **NGOs and civic initiatives** focusing on climate resilience, education, and environmental protection (e.g., We4All, EcoGenia, Resilient Planet) were contacted to broaden the dialogue and involve grassroots actors.
5. **Media Representatives**. The invitation was distributed to a range of **national and European media outlets**, including editors, journalists, and digital platforms specializing in environment, climate action, and sustainability reporting.
6. **European Environmental Networks and Projects**. A significant part of the promotional effort targeted actors already involved in **European-funded environmental initiatives**. The outreach aimed to build connections between NEUROCLIMA and relevant communities across Europe engaged in climate education, adaptation, green transition, and civic engagement. The recipient categories included:
 - **Consortia and participants of Horizon Europe and LIFE projects** working on climate resilience, behaviour change, and sustainable urban development (e.g., ARSINOE, REGILIENCE, LIFE ASTI, LIFE Adaptablues).
 - **Climate science and policy networks**, including JPI Climate, CICERO (Norway), and sectoral projects under the European Green Deal and Mission Adaptation programmes.
 - **European climate governance stakeholders**, such as European Commission officials, national Climate Pact Ambassadors (emails addressed per country), and experts participating in the EU Climate Pact community.
 - **Academic researchers and institutions** engaged in environmental studies and climate modelling (e.g., University of Oslo, University of Antwerp, EURECAT, NTUA, University of Athens, University of Cyprus).
 - **Civil society organisations and networks** active in climate justice, sustainability, and youth engagement across Europe and associated countries, including ECOLISE, Zero Waste Europe, WWF, ClientEarth, Greenpeace, Friends of the Earth, and others.
 - **Municipalities and local governance stakeholders**, particularly from Central and Eastern Europe, involved in local climate strategies and EU-level cooperation (e.g., through Urban Transitions Mission, Covenant of Mayors, or Erasmus+ mobility projects).

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- **Environmental education networks and teacher associations**, such as national or regional pedagogical coordinators (e.g., ΠΕΕΚΠΕ, ΕΛΕΕΤΡΕΑ), educational media, and school networks focused on environmental literacy.
- **Private and public communication experts**, designers, facilitators, and independent consultants engaged in participatory methodologies and awareness campaigns in the environmental field.

This targeted and multilayered outreach reinforced the connection between NEUROCLIMA and the wider European landscape of climate governance and participatory environmental action. The diversity of recipients reflects the project’s interdisciplinary character and its ambition to act as a collaborative platform for knowledge exchange and practice co-design.

Registration Process

Registration was managed through a streamlined online form. Participants completed a short form and immediately received a confirmation email with the Zoom participation link. The form required only essential information (name, email, country/region, and organisation) to lower access barriers and prioritise inclusiveness. Upon registration, participants were informed that their data would be processed in accordance with the privacy policy of IASIS (<https://www.iasismed.eu/πολιτική-προστασίας-προσωπικών-δεδο/>) and consent was obtained for their data to be shared with the host and account owner, as per the platform’s Terms and Privacy Policy.

The communication tone of the campaign was accessible and open. Rather than focusing on reach alone, the aim was to attract participants who could meaningfully engage with the NEUROCLIMA approach and contribute to shaping the next phase of development.

The pre-event registration dataset includes 95 participants. This number reflects substantial early engagement with NEUROCLIMA’s digital tools on climate resilience. The sign-ups span across multiple countries and sectors, showing broad geographic and professional interest.

Total Registrations

A total of **95 individuals** registered for the workshop.

Table 1. Daily Registration Trends

Date	Registrations
April 21, 2025	3
April 22, 2025	28
April 23, 2025	24
April 24, 2025	19
April 25, 2025	5
April 26, 2025	2
April 27, 2025	3
April 28, 2025	11

The highest registration activity occurred on April 22 and 23. This suggests that communication and visibility efforts during these days were effective.

Table 2. Country Distribution

Country	Participants
Greece (GR)	37
Italy (IT)	7
Cyprus (CY)	7
Romania (RO)	6
Belgium (BE)	6
Poland (PL)	4
Spain (ES)	3
Bulgaria (BG)	3
Ireland (IE)	3
Slovakia (SK)	2
Austria (AT)	2
Netherlands (NL)	2
France (FR)	2
UAE (AE)	1
Portugal (PT)	1
Turkey (TR)	1
Finland (FI)	1
Luxembourg (LU)	1
UK (GB)	1
USA (US)	1
Estonia (EE)	1
Slovenia (SI)	1
Switzerland (CH)	1
Ukraine (UA)	1

Greek participants represent around 39% of the total, which is expected due to IASIS’s hosting role. Southern and Eastern Europe are well represented. A few registrations came from non-European regions (USA, UAE), reflecting wider interest in climate resilience tools beyond the project’s regional focus. Removing all participants affiliated with NEUROCLIMA consortium members gives a dataset of **81 fully external registrations**. This reflects genuine outside interest in the initiative.

Table 3. External Participant Distribution

Country	Participants
---------	--------------

Greece (GR)	29
Romania (RO)	6
Cyprus (CY)	6
Italy (IT)	6
Poland (PL)	4
Bulgaria (BG)	3
Ireland (IE)	3
Belgium (BE)	3
Spain (ES)	2
Slovakia (SK)	2
Austria (AT)	2
Netherlands (NL)	2
France (FR)	2
Portugal (PT)	1
UAE (AE)	1
Turkey (TR)	1
Finland (FI)	1
USA (US)	1
UK (GB)	1
Slovenia (SI)	1
Switzerland (CH)	1
Luxembourg (LU)	1
Estonia (EE)	1
Ukraine (UA)	1

The international dimension remains strong, covering 24 countries.

External Organizations Represented

Participants represented a diverse range of entities, including academic institutions, public sector bodies, private companies, non-governmental organisations, and independent professionals. In total, over 50 organisations were represented. All personal and institutional data were processed in accordance with the IASIS Privacy Policy and were used exclusively for purposes directly related to the organisation, implementation, and reporting of the workshop.

Observations

- The workshop drew attention beyond the immediate NEUROCLIMA network.
- The participation reflects multiple sectors, including education, environmental policy, civil society, journalism, public governance, and tech.
- The presence of non-EU participants, although small, is promising for future scaling and visibility.
-

Table 4. Final Registered Participants Overview

Metric	Value
Total Registrants	95
External Registrants	81
Top Registration Date	April 22, 2025
Leading Country (All)	Greece (37 participants)
Leading Country (External)	Greece (29 participants)
Country Coverage (External)	24 countries

3.2.3 Final Participant Attendance Analysis

The NEUROCLIMA stakeholder workshop held on 29 April 2025 finally brought together **51 confirmed participants**. While the number is lower than the 95 who originally registered, it reflects meaningful and active engagement across sectors and geographies. Importantly, **a clear majority of attendees came from outside the project consortium**, highlighting the strength of the dissemination effort and the resonance of NEUROCLIMA’s themes with a broader audience. The diversity of participants—geographical, institutional, and professional—provided depth to the discussions. The representation of countries from both within and beyond the European Union shows that NEUROCLIMA’s ideas travel well across borders.

Participants joined from **18 countries**, with a strong presence from Southern and Eastern Europe. The distribution is as follows:

Table 5. Final Participants per Country

Country	Participants
Greece (GR)	15
Cyprus (CY)	5
Belgium (BE)	4
Italy (IT)	4
Bulgaria (BG)	3
Spain (ES)	3
Austria (AT)	2
Poland (PL)	2
Ireland (IE)	2
Finland (FI)	2
France (FR)	2
Switzerland (CH)	1

Romania (RO)	1
Ukraine (UA)	1
Estonia (EE)	1
UAE (AE)	1
USA (US)	1
Luxembourg (LU)	1

Greece, as the host country and a leading consortium partner, had the highest representation. However, the balance across other countries—both EU and non-EU—points to growing interest in NEUROCLIMA’s work from different regions. In total, **18 countries were represented by external participants**, showing wide geographical reach. The participants reflected a **broad mix of sectors**, including environmental policy, education, civil society, research, innovation, and public governance. This diversity added real value to the workshop, ensuring that the perspectives shared during discussions were grounded in a range of real-world contexts.

The workshop brought together representatives from a wide array of organisations operating across Europe, including entities active in environmental innovation, digital technologies, public administration, academic research, and civic engagement. Participation reflected a balanced mix of governmental bodies, universities, private sector actors, and civil society initiatives. All data were processed in line with the IASIS Privacy Policy and used solely for the organisation and documentation of the event.

Many participants joined in a personal or professional capacity. Some were educators, others were researchers, community activists, or innovation specialists.

Key Observations

- **35 out of 51 participants (69%) were external to the consortium**, indicating strong interest beyond the project's internal stakeholders.
- Greek participation was notable but proportionate, accounting for **29%** of all attendees.
- The presence of both large institutions and smaller civil society actors underlines NEUROCLIMA’s capacity to reach a wide range of audiences.
- Participation was relatively well distributed across countries and sectors, without overrepresentation from any single group.

The final attendance shows not just visibility, but **genuine engagement**. People showed up, participated, and interacted—not because they had to, but because the content mattered to them. This indicates a level of **trust and relevance** that cannot be forced through formal outreach alone. It’s also encouraging to see smaller, often underrepresented organisations and individuals attending. This signals openness and accessibility—two central pillars of NEUROCLIMA’s engagement strategy. For future workshops, the focus should be on sustaining these connections and enhancing the **conversion rate from registration to participation**. Clear follow-up actions, personalised invitations, and interactive formats may further strengthen participation rates and community building.

Table 6. Workshop Participation Overview

Metric	Value
--------	-------

Total Registrants	95
Final Attendance	51
External Registrants	35
Country Coverage (External)	18 countries

3.2.4 Participants' Feedback

Real-time feedback was gathered during the workshop through the interactive platform Wooclap. Participants were invited to share their impressions immediately after each tool demonstration. This approach allowed for spontaneous, experience-based responses and created a dynamic link between content and evaluation. In total, 46 participants contributed at least one response during the session.

The group included educators (42%), policy-makers (19%), journalists (19%), and a broad range of other professionals such as researchers, community facilitators, consultants, and public officials (27%). This diversity reflects the interdisciplinary character of the NEUROCLIMA approach and its resonance with audiences across sectors.

The tools presented—NeuroClimaLens, NeuroClimaBot, NeuroClimaDialogues, NeuroClimaLearn, and NeuroClimaPlay—were assessed in terms of usefulness, ease of use, and relevance to the participants' fields. The feedback was consistent and generally positive, with each tool offering a different value proposition depending on the user's profile and professional context.

NeuroClimaLens was considered especially relevant for journalists and educators. Seventy-four percent of respondents agreed that it could help content creators develop climate adaptation material, and 68% saw it as useful for educational planning. Its filtering, summarisation, and semantic search functions were well received, although some comments highlighted the need for further emphasis on the accuracy of its sources and relevance to policy.

NeuroClimaBot received high scores for accessibility and adaptability. Most participants found it intuitive, with 89% rating it as easy to use and quick to learn. Its multilingual capability and natural language interface were praised, especially by educators who noted its value for inclusive teaching and public engagement. Responses also pointed to the bot's potential for addressing common misconceptions and supporting critical thinking.

NeuroClimaDialogues stood out for its structured design and capacity to foster inclusive discussion. Eighty percent of respondents felt it could effectively support participatory policymaking, though some also noted that facilitation would be necessary to ensure equity in large-scale deliberative settings. The tool's visual interface and integrated feedback options were seen as useful for both public and institutional use.

NeuroClimaLearn attracted interest from educators who valued its modular structure and potential for both formal and informal learning. Seventy-five percent agreed it was easy to navigate and adaptable to different contexts. Its strength lies in its ability to link local knowledge with broader environmental literacy goals, offering a space where co-created content can be shared and reused across regions.

Feedback on **NeuroClimaPlay** was limited during the session, likely due to timing. However, informal comments in the chat expressed interest in the use of gamification, especially for engaging younger

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audiences in emotionally safe and participatory learning experiences. Future sessions may benefit from allocating more time to explore this component in depth.

Participants were also asked whether they would recommend the overall NEUROCLIMA digital solution. All respondents answered positively, with an average rating of 4.5 out of 5. Notably, none of the participants reported being familiar with similar tools, suggesting a strong innovation value. As one comment noted, existing platforms tend to be “far less complete,” lacking the integration and coherence offered by NEUROCLIMA.

The tone throughout the session remained open and constructive. Questions posed in the chat demonstrated curiosity, critical thinking, and a willingness to contribute. Several participants expressed interest in co-creating materials, while others emphasised the importance of scientific rigour, clarity of language, and educational integration.

Overall, the feedback confirmed that NEUROCLIMA is seen not only as technically sound but also as socially relevant and professionally useful. The interactive format and sequencing of the event supported engagement, while the tools themselves were received as adaptable, user-centred, and aligned with the project’s broader aims of behavioural and systemic change. The results will guide the next phase of refinement, ensuring that the solution continues to respond to real needs, practices, and expectations.

3.2.5 Reflections from the Chat: Engagement, Participation, and Emerging Themes

The live chat on Zoom offered a valuable window into the tone, responsiveness, and depth of participant engagement throughout the NEUROCLIMA workshop. Rather than operating as a passive communication channel, the chat evolved into a dynamic space for exchange, with attendees sharing resources, posing questions, and engaging in constructive dialogue. This added a second layer of interactivity to the event, reinforcing the human-centred and participatory spirit of NEUROCLIMA.

Participants used the chat not only to respond in real time to presentations but also to initiate peer-to-peer interaction. Useful links were circulated during the session, including access to the project website and the NEUROCLIMA newsletter, while tools like Wooclap were used to support immediate feedback. These actions contributed to a sense of shared ownership and helped shift the session from a one-way delivery model to a more collaborative digital environment.

The questions raised were not generic. They reflected genuine interest in the project’s direction and its underlying assumptions. One participant inquired about opportunities for direct involvement in co-creation processes, while another focused on the importance of scientific credibility—asking how the project ensures that its tools deliver verified, evidence-based content. A third raised a practical point about the integration between components of the digital solution, namely the Lens and the Bot, highlighting an interest in how tools interact rather than function in isolation.

Beyond the substantive contributions, the chat revealed a warm and respectful tone among participants. Comments expressing gratitude, encouragement, and curiosity appeared frequently, especially during the closing moments of the workshop. While these interactions may seem informal, they carry significance: they reflect how the session was received emotionally, not just intellectually. They also reinforce the project's emphasis on climate resilience as both a cognitive and affective journey.

Technically, the session ran smoothly, with only minor disruptions reported. Moderators responded promptly to occasional visibility concerns, ensuring participants could follow the presentations without

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difficulty. Behind-the-scenes coordination by IASIS and partner teams contributed to a seamless experience, which likely supported the overall satisfaction levels recorded in the workshop feedback.

Some of the most compelling exchanges in the chat came from educators, who asked whether NEUROCLIMA content could be adapted for classroom use. This interest confirms the educational relevance of the tools and suggests clear demand for integration into school-based learning. It also underscores the project's potential to support curriculum innovation and address eco-emotions in structured, developmentally appropriate ways.

A key takeaway from the chat was the diversity of perspectives. Contributors from Greece, Estonia, Poland, and elsewhere brought lived experiences into the conversation, connecting climate tools with real-world narratives. One reference to the Varaküps documentary opened a short but meaningful discussion on the emotional layers of climate work, offering a reminder that adaptation is not only a technical challenge but also a deeply human process.

The chat also highlighted participants' demand for reliable, validated knowledge. Several comments returned to the question of source credibility, especially in relation to tools like the Bot and Lens. This aligns with the broader project commitment to transparency, evidence-based development, and user trust.

In summary, the chat functioned as a parallel space of engagement that mirrored and enriched the main content of the session. It offered spontaneous feedback, surfaced practical questions, and fostered a sense of community. Most importantly, it showed that the project's messages resonate with audiences who are not just listening but willing to think, respond, and contribute.

3.2.6 Continued Dissemination and Open Access to Content

Dissemination activities have continued beyond the live delivery of the workshop. To ensure wider reach and long-term accessibility, the full session—*Climate Resilience Blueprints: A First Look at NEUROCLIMA's Digital Solution*—was recorded and is now publicly available. The video is hosted on the official NEUROCLIMA website at <https://neuroclima.eu/workshop-climate-resilience-blueprints-recording/> and also on the project's YouTube channel at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=waaSiZv6pt0>.

The recording strictly follows all applicable ethical and privacy standards. No participants are shown or personally identifiable, ensuring that the session remains accessible while fully respecting attendees' anonymity and consent.

Making the workshop content available in this format supports NEUROCLIMA's broader goals of openness, transparency, and inclusive climate dialogue. The recording serves as both documentation and a resource for educators, policymakers, civil society actors, and citizens interested in the project's tools and approaches.

3.3 External Dissemination and Synergistic Activities

NEUROCLIMA has always aimed to reach beyond its consortium. From the start of the project, there was a strong focus on involving not just technical partners but also wider networks—such as institutions, civil society groups, and knowledge communities. Three major public events clearly show this commitment to inclusive and forward-looking outreach.

I. Tech(&)Democracy: Conversations at the Crossroads of Technology and Democracy

- **Date & Place:** 14 October 2024, Milan, Italy
- **Organised by:** NEUROCLIMA and the Horizon Europe project ORBIS, as part of Milano Digital Week. Hosted by Fondazione Giangiacomo Feltrinelli.

This event explored the connection between new technologies and democracy. It aimed to strengthen collaboration between NEUROCLIMA and ORBIS and to reach new audiences, including policymakers, researchers, and civil society organisations.

Three key discussions were held: how AI and digital platforms can support public decision-making; why it's important for people to understand how data and algorithms are used; and real-life examples of using AI in inclusive and evidence-based public dialogue.

The event helped test early ideas, gather feedback, and build future partnerships. It also produced materials for further sharing and helped connect NEUROCLIMA with new communities.

II. The Hydrosphere in Focus: Safeguarding Water for a Sustainable Future

- **Date & Place:** 27 March 2025, online
- **Organised by:** Verimpart and the Institute for Sustainable Development – EPLO, in partnership with Truenique and NEUROCLIMA.

This online webinar brought together climate experts, educators, policymakers, and citizens to talk about the importance of water in adapting to climate change. Discussions included relevant policy frameworks, scientific tools, and local strategies for better water governance.

The event provided a practical and accessible way for participants to engage with climate adaptation topics and helped position NEUROCLIMA in larger discussions on environmental justice and Europe's green transition.

III. NEUROCLIMA at *CONSUMAI*.

- **Date & Place:** 25 March 2025, in person, Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy
- **Organised by:** NINA (Neither Intelligent Neither Artificial), a civil society organization working on the cultural and political impacts of AI across sectors - in Partnership with Resilient Global Action Project (G.A.P.) and Politecnico di Milano.

This event, brought together citizens, students, researchers interested in the topic of AI and Environment engaging in an open discussion revolving around the core question: what is the relationship between the rapid development of artificial intelligence, its growing energy demands, and the unfolding climate crisis? A dedicated post can be found on our website, too.

<https://neuroclima.eu/consumai-event-polimi/>

IV. NEUROCLIMA at the BioMed AI Summer School 2025

- **Date & Place:** 27 May 2025, IARC/WHO Headquarters, Lyon, France
- **Organised by:** Truenique (NEUROCLIMA partner), as part of the 2025 BioMed AI Summer School.

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NEUROCLIMA was presented to an international group of professionals from computer science, biotechnology, academia, and policy. The presentation used a short version of the “Digital Blueprints” format first shared in April. An online poll was held during the session, and participants were invited to complete a Google Form to give consent for future contact.

Despite the session lasting only 40 minutes, 42 people completed the poll and 20 signed the consent form, representing 12 countries. Many participants expressed strong interest in working with the tools and joining future workshops. Some researchers highlighted how NEUROCLIMA Lens could be useful for training on climate change, and two EU-funded projects expressed interest in using NeuroClimaLearn to share their course content.

Policymakers, including from the European Parliament, were interested in holding a dedicated workshop for MEPs once the tools are fully developed. A follow-up session is already planned for next year’s BioMed AI Summer School at UZA in Antwerp, where the tools will be presented in more depth.

V. NEUROCLIMA at the STSItalia Conference - AI&Democracy Panel

- **Date & Place:** 13 June 2025, in person, Politecnico di Milano, Department of Design, Italy
- **Organised by:** Politecnico di Milano, Department of Design

NEUROCLIMA was presented to an international group of researchers from social sciences, design, politics and policy. During the panel “Speculative Futures and New Scenarios for Systemic Change, Participatory Design, Reconfiguring Democracy,” NEUROCLIMA’s team presented its “nervous system” framework, illustrating how a hybrid of digital and analog tools can empower citizens in deliberative processes. The session opened with an overview of speculative futures methods, inviting panelists a participants to envision alternative climate-resilient democracies

These five events increased NEUROCLIMA’s visibility, allowed it to test its ideas in real settings, and opened new opportunities for collaboration. More importantly, they helped NEUROCLIMA connect with people and organisations outside its core group—such as local authorities, NGOs, research institutions, and community groups.

This way of working—combining sharing with participation—shows NEUROCLIMA’s overall approach: real impact means not just reaching people, but involving them meaningfully, inclusively, and usefully.

4. Mapping Relevant EU Projects and Collaborative Synergies

A structured mapping of European projects aligned with the thematic focus of NEUROCLIMA is conducted to support knowledge exchange and strategic collaboration. The objective of this mapping is twofold: to identify ongoing initiatives that apply relevant approaches to climate resilience and behavioural change, and to establish potential synergies for sharing knowledge and practices.

Several projects are approached and informed about the NEUROCLIMA online workshop, while two—Mission4Adapt: Agora and Pro-Climate—are actively engaged in bilateral synergy meetings.

The **Pro-Climate project** (<https://pro-climate.eu/>) focuses on proactive community adaptation through social transformation and behavioural change. It explores social tipping points and designs policy actions that support systemic adaptation. The synergy meeting with the Pro-Climate team allows alignment of behavioural approaches and facilitates the exchange of perspectives on community-level interventions.

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The **Agora** initiative (<https://agoracommunity.org/>), operating under the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, works to promote inclusive governance and accelerate local adaptation using proven methodologies and participatory tools. During the synergy meeting with the Agora team, both sides share experiences on stakeholder engagement and regionally embedded practices, contributing to a deeper mutual understanding of the barriers and drivers in community-based adaptation.

The **CARMINE project** (<https://carmine-project.eu/>) co-develops a knowledge-based framework to address adaptation and mitigation across eight metropolitan regions in Europe. It bridges the gap between science and practice by co-creating actionable tools, products, and services that strengthen climate resilience at the local level and support decision-making across Europe. Consultations are currently underway with CARMINE, particularly with the pilot in the Athens Metropolitan Area, to explore collaborative opportunities between the two projects.

In parallel, several additional projects with thematic relevance are reviewed:

- **CLIMAS** (<https://www.climas-project.eu/>): Uses climate assemblies and living labs to enhance participatory policymaking. It provides a co-designed toolbox for climate adaptation based on shared values, design thinking, and citizen science.
- **TransformAr** (<https://transformar.eu/>): Develops rapid adaptation pathways through cross-sectoral innovation that supports regional climate transitions.
- **Oceanidis** (<https://www.oceanids-project.eu/>): Focuses on maritime spatial planning tools to improve resilience in coastal areas.
- **MountAdapt** (<https://mountadapt.eu/>): Addresses health and environmental challenges in mountainous regions under climate change.

Additional projects with strong thematic alignment include:

- **Regions4Climate** (<https://regions4climate.eu/>): Develops socially just roadmaps and integrated innovations for regional adaptation.
- **REGILIENCE** (<https://regilience.eu/>): Supports regional climate resilience through the promotion of tools and knowledge across European contexts.
- **I-CHANGE** (<https://iequalchange.com/>): Demonstrates the potential of behavioural change through citizen science supported by sensors.
- **ORBIS** (<https://orbis-project.eu/>): Advances inclusive deliberative democracy through digital models and socio-technical frameworks.
- **MAIA** (<https://maia-project.eu/>): Strengthens the impact of climate research by linking platforms and increasing access to innovation.
- **Pathways2Resilience** (<https://www.pathways2resilience.eu/>): Accompanies at least 150 European regions in building capacity and action plans for climate resilience.
- **ACHIEVE** (<https://www.achieveproject.eu/>): Investigates voluntary climate action as a path to net-zero targets, integrating science and policy alignment.
- **IMPETUS** (<https://climate-impetus.eu/>): Promotes local climate adaptation by co-developing inclusive solutions with communities and stakeholders.
- **1.5 Lifestyles** (<https://onepointfivelifestyles.eu/>): Examines how lifestyle changes at the individual level can align with the 1.5°C climate target.
- **CROSSEU** (<https://crosseu.eu/>): Provides decision-makers with cross-sectoral tools to address climate-related risks.
- **ARSINOE** (<https://arsinoe-project.eu/>): Combines systems innovation with climate solution platforms to support regional adaptation strategies.

This project mapping directly supports NEUROCLIMA's scaling mechanism and strengthens its engagement strategy by connecting with key European actors working on climate adaptation, citizen participation, and systemic change.

5. Conclusions

The first phase of Task T7.3 created a solid foundation for NEUROCLIMA's stakeholder engagement and community-building strategy. It included internal workshops, a large-scale online event, and a comprehensive mapping of related EU projects. These activities offered clear insights that will directly shape the next steps.

The internal workshops improved coordination between partners and strengthened a shared ethical and methodological approach. They also helped refine NEUROCLIMA's tools for behavioural change and inclusive participation. These tools were later tested in the external workshop, which gathered 51 confirmed participants from 24 countries. Feedback confirmed the relevance of the tools, while also highlighting the need for more face-to-face and moderated interaction.

The workshop revealed key conditions for effective engagement: digital platforms must be accessible, transparent, and clearly linked to real-world outcomes. Participants valued the clarity of the tools, but stressed that trust depends on human presence and open dialogue. This will guide the transition toward hybrid and in-person events in the next phase of T7.3.

The outreach to related EU projects confirmed that NEUROCLIMA is aligned with major European efforts on climate resilience and behavioural transformation. Synergy meetings with *Pro-Climate* and *Agora* showed a clear interest in collaboration, especially in the areas of participatory methods and community-level adaptation. These connections will now be further developed into concrete joint actions and shared dissemination efforts.

The continuation of Task T7.3 will focus on three priorities:

- Deepening relationships with workshop participants through structured follow-up.
- Organising in-person and hybrid engagements to enhance trust and co-creation.
- Activating a community of practice that connects NEUROCLIMA with other EU initiatives.

This task is not limited to information-sharing. It is designed to build lasting dialogue and support practical tools for adaptation. The next stage will apply lessons learned to reinforce local relevance, test inclusive facilitation methods in real-world settings, and support ongoing collaboration beyond the project's lifecycle.

ANNEX I - Photos

Tech and Democracy

ConsumAI

LE PREVISIONI DEI TEMPI

Il collettivo Ninea ritorna con un secondo ciclo di otto incontri sull'intelligenza artificiale. Parleremo e ci confronteremo su quanto come e perché l'AI influenzi già - e possa in futuro influenzare - tanti e differenti ambiti della nostra vita, dai servizi primari (come la sanità o l'educazione) alla dimensione comunitaria e collettiva. Discuteremo della creazione e diffusione delle fake news e delle post verità, della guerra, dell'impatto sulla giustizia ambientale e del controllo sociale. Dentro uno scenario complesso in cui anche la creatività diventa computabile, noi diciamo viva fincomputabile e costruiamo relazioni reali per capire il presente e pensare in modo diverso il valore del vivente e del non vivente.

more info

martedì 25/03
ore 18:15
Politecnico di Milano
piazza Leonardo da Vinci, 32
edificio 9, aula 9.O.1

ConsumAI

quale rapporto tra sviluppo dell'intelligenza artificiale, energia e clima?

no discutono
Bastrice Gobbo assegnata di ricerca dipartimento Design, Politecnico di Milano, Team di Coordinamento progetto Horizon Europe Neuroclima
Silvio Gualdi Principal Scientist presso Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici e direttore della Divisione Earth System Modelling and Data Assimilation
Caterina Orsenigo giornalista ambientale
Gianluca Ruggieri ricercatore, Università dell'Insubria
Roberto Verdecchia ricercatore di Ingegneria del Software, Università degli Studi di Firenze

modera
Jacopo Casadei Ninea.

In collaborazione con

POLITECNICO DI MILANO - DIPARTIMENTO NEUROCLIMA

Funded by the European Union

NE INTELLIGENTE NE ARTIFICIALE

Climate Resilience Blueprints: A First Look at NEUROCLIMA's Digital Solution

NEUROCLIMA Climate Resilience Blueprints

NEUROCLIMA

Developing and assessing novel educational and user-centred actions towards scaling up behavioural change and climate resilience through an AI-enhanced solution.

Non dispone dell'autorizzazione per riprodurre l'oggetto multimediale in questa presentazione. Visualizza per richiedere l'accesso

NEUROCLIMA has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under the Grant Agreement No.101137711

Let's try a sample module here

Quiz

Divide the good from the wrong practices for saving water during your every-day life.

Water your garden frequently

Good practices

Shower with less water

Bad practices

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NEUROCLIMA Reference Architecture

AI and Analytics (Tier 2)

- Policy observatory (NC-AS-PO)
- Search engine
- Resource accumulator

KG semantic enrichment (NC-AS-KGSE)

- Enrichment sub-component
- Data structuring for visualizations

Automatic data composing and dialogue generation (NC-AS-ADCG)

- NeuroClimateLangChain

Policy observatory (Tier 1)

Policy observatory (Tier 2)

Policy observatory (Tier 3)

Policy observatory (Tier 4)

Policy observatory (Tier 5)

Policy observatory (Tier 6)

Policy observatory (Tier 7)

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NeuroClimaBot: Smart Conversational Agent for Climate Resilience

A sophisticated AI-powered conversational agent within the NeuroClima system, designed to enhance decision-making and raise public awareness on climate change adaptation.

Key Features:

- Multilingual Conversational Interface:** Interact in English, Italian, Greek, and Portuguese with voice-enabled responses for improved accessibility.
- Natural Language Climate Data Search:** Ask questions or use keywords to explore climate topics across news, policies, and scientific papers.
- Smart Summarization & Document Linking:** Receive concise summaries via responses with direct access to full documents for deeper insights.
- Context-Aware, Domain-Specific Assistance:** Tailored support for climate adaptation using advanced NLP, NLU, and LLMs.
- Dual RAG Strategy (Naive + Graph RAG):** Combines basic retrieval and graph-enhanced context to boost relevance and coherence of responses.
- Identifies Social Tipping Points (STPs):** Detects key leverage areas that may trigger major societal shifts in climate adaptation.
- Reduced Hallucination via Real-Time Grounding:** Uses live data retrieval to generate fact-based, reliable responses.
- Readability Toggle & Copyable Responses:** Switch between complex or simplified language and copy answers for reuse.
- User Feedback & Engagement Tools:** Like/dislike buttons and a feedback tab support continuous improvement and user satisfaction tracking.
- Audio Playback of Responses:** Listen to chatbot answers for a multimodal and accessible experience.

Listen to chatbot answers for a multimodal and accessible experience. Horizon Europe programme under the Grant Agreement No 101137211

User Name	Feedback	Pages	Likes	Shares	Last Activity
Demetris Tsakalidis	0/0	0	1197	0	27/03/2025
Fanny Boudin	0	0	0	1	27/03/2025
Maria Papadimitrakopoulou	0/0	0	1116	141	27/03/2025
Athina Karavelidou	0	0	0	4	26/03/2025
Josiah Johnson	0	14	0	1	24/03/2025
Miriam Whittaker	0	0	1	0	24/03/2025
Yvonne Koudou	0/0	0	1000	173	20/03/2025
George Domalis	2/7	0	1024	106	19/03/2025
Alex Koudou	0/1	0	1000	143	19/03/2025
George Domalis	0	0	1001	113	19/03/2025

Finally, the Users section offers insights into participation patterns.

NeuroClimaLearn
From Climate Literacy to Climate Leadership.

What is NeuroClima Learn?

- Flexible Learning, Real-World Impact/ an LMS platform
- Courses become Creative Tools for Climate Action
- Leveraging NeuroClima ICT/ empowering educators
- Journalists, Policymakers, Citizens hosting courses
- Building a Climate-Resilient Community together

NEUROCLIMA has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under the Grant Agreement No 101137711

Antonis Batsos

verimpact

Christina Deligianni

Cinematherapy Toolkit

Purpose: To process eco-anxiety, grief, and adaptive stress using cinematic narratives that mirror environmental realities.

Methodological Steps (Dermer & Hutchings, 2000; Huerta, 2018):

1. **Assessment** – Identify emotional states; select relevant films (e.g., Ice Age).
2. **Film Viewing** – Screen films in facilitated sessions; participants reflect on emotions and symbolism.
3. **Debriefing & Reflection** – Discuss character metaphors in relation to climate displacement or resilience.
4. **Creative Output** – Participants create their own short films or storyboards representing personal adaptation journeys.

Climate Resilience Blueprints

NEUROCLIMA has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under the Grant Agreement No 101137711

IASIS NGO (Greece)

NEUROCLIMA Workshop: Climate Resilience Blueprints: A First Look at NEUROCLIMA’s Digital Solution

Date & Time Apr 29, 2025 03:30 PM in Zurich

Meeting Registration

First Name*

This field is required.

Last Name*

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Email Address*

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Organization*

Information you provide when registering will be shared with the [account owner](#) and host and can be used and shared by them in accordance with their Terms and Privacy Policy.

Register

2025 BioMed AI Summer School

Deliverable D7.5: Proceedings of NEUROCLIMA Workshops and Summary Report on Cohesion Activities 1

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